

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Kamalova Lobar Yagmurovna

PHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS OF RATIONAL NUTRITION AND DAILY INTAKE

OF NUTRIENTS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

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